

35. Staycation Post-pandemic: The Experiential Tourism in Malaysia

Chong Kim Mee ¹, Tan Tze Horng ² and Rashid Ating ³

¹ SEGi University & Colleges, Graduate School of Business (GSB), Malaysia

² Riam Institute of Technology, School of Business, Malaysia

³ Universiti Malaya, Institute of Advanced Studies (IAS), Malaysia

*Correspondence: chongkimmee@segi.edu.my

Keywords: Staycation; Experiential tourism; Post-pandemic; Domestic tourism; Malaysia

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

According to World Economic Forum (2021), workers daily stress reached a record high in 2020. Workers in US and Canada showed the highest level of daily stress, with 57% in 2020. The COVID-19 pandemic has highly impacted the personal well-being and social and working life of millions of people globally. Malaysians reported the highest level of anxiety among 12,823 employed online adults aged 16-74 across 28 countries between November and December 2020 based on research conducted by Ipsos on its Global Advisor online platform (Ipsos Malaysia, 2021). There is an unexpectedly high percentage of Malaysians who experienced increased anxiety around job security at 74% compared to a global share of 56%, and stress due to changes in work routines and organization at 67% compared to a worldwide percentage of 55%, respectively. Besides, 10% of the employees lost their jobs, and 7% of employees chose to leave their jobs during this COVID-19 pandemic at the end of 2020 in Malaysia. Although stress is a potential killer to a person's health and well-being, several studies have shown that seven consecutive vacation days provided an efficient recovery strategy.

Blank et al. (2018) stated that one single short-term vacation with independent mode brings significant, positive, and immediate effects on perceived stress, recovery, and well-being. A staycation, a road trip, and a meeting with someone at the local destination are believed to reduce stress. Experiential travel, which focuses on experience quality rather than quantity, is getting increasingly attractive to visitors or travelers especially post COVID-19. The interaction with local people, culture and environment brings value to the visitors. Experiential tourism differs from other traveling modes on direct experience during pre-departure trip planning and post-trip follow-up, including the people they met, the places visited, the activities participated in, and the memories created. Moreover, personal growth and reflection of individuals' values and interests are essential to experiential tourism as emotional experience is associated with vivid memory, the feeling of the destination place and revisiting intention is more important than tangible goods we can purchase.

According to the survey on domestic travel in Malaysia since the recovery movement control order (RMCO) in assessing the domestic demand for leisure travel from September to October 2020, 75.2% of the total of 12,281 respondents planned for domestic travel shortly after the promotion of interstate traveling since June 10, 2020, by the Malaysia government. 74.7% of the respondents arranged their leisure holidays alone, and 87.0% purchased their holiday through online booking sites. Only 10.5% of the respondents purchased their holiday through travel agencies or tour operators. Besides, the highest percentage of 51.6% of the respondents preferred to travel during the weekend or long weekends other than on weekdays, public holidays, and festival holidays. It is believed that Malaysians generally have limited time to go for leisure due to their hectic work schedule and children's studies. Based on research by Bilgihan (2016), hedonism also relates to online spending, and when a positive experience has been created, it will lead to loyalty. For example, the staycation

goers who booked online and are satisfied with the experience will have a positive attitude towards staycation. As such, hedonism is vital for online staycation booking as it happens in a comfortable environment with a relaxed attitude and enjoyment with shopping intentions (Wagner et al., 2016). Furthermore, entertainment directly affects attitudes (Childers et al., 2002). Thus, it is assumed that the higher the hedonic motivation towards the staycation, the higher level of decreased anxiety and stress levels.

One of the most influential theories of human behavior is the social cognitive theory, which serves as the theory for this study (Bandura, 1986). One of the basic concepts of social cognitive theory stipulates that the person regulates behavior through the process and the environment through external social situations (Cooper & Lu, 2016). As such, going for a staycation through a series of techniques such as searching, evaluating, and booking the staycation is considered a social interaction that helps to reduce stress levels, and experiencing a staycation comfortably will further enhance the feel-good experience, according to Bandura (1991) one of the components of social cognitive theory is behavior change when people react or respond to a particular situation or object.

Domestic tourism spending fell 54.5%, recorded RM 18.4 billion in 2021 compared to RM 40.4 billion in 2020, which showed the lowest record since 2008, the first year of the survey report (Domestic Tourism Malaysia, 2021). The border restrictions on new variants of COVID-19, such as Omicron and Delta, continued to impact domestic tourism in 2021, and the floods disaster towards the end of 2021 in many parts of Peninsular Malaysia caused domestic travel to worsen. In addition, the overnight trip had decreased by 67.8%, with 15.5 million visits, while daily trips decreased by 42.4%, with 56.9 million trips recorded in 2021.

However, due to the closure of Malaysia's international border, the statistics showed a significant increase in domestic visitors with a household income of RM 5,001 to RM 10,000, with the highest contribution of 30.4% in 2021 from the pre-pandemic year, at 23.3% in 2019. In contrast, there is a decrease of 6.4% from 2019 to a record of 29.3% of the domestic visitors travel by household income between RM 1,001 and RM 3,000. Malaysia's domestic travel industry is likely to recover with the transition to the endemic phase, as announced by the government, which will lead to positive growth in 2022.

This study explores the determinants of experiential tourism in the context of staycation among the M40 group, where the household income fell under RM 4,851 to RM 10,970 per month. There are 37.2% of the Malaysian population with a mean of RM 7,348 household income per month, which are categorized under M1, M2, M3 and M4, contributing to 6.8%, 8.2%, 9.9% and 12.3%, with median income of RM 5,336, RM 6,471, RM 7,828, and RM 9,695 respectively (Department of Statistics, Malaysia, 2019).

Using the purposive sampling technique, a self-administered questionnaire was given to 300 respondents: 150 in West Malaysia and 150 in East Malaysia. As this study used a quantitative approach, a further in-depth analysis using a qualitative approach should be conducted. This study contributes to Malaysia's tourism industries and policymakers targeting and servicing the M40 group of preference. It also highlights the market demand from the local experiential tourism perspectives. Stress levels can be reduced among the middle group after experiencing a staycation or short vacation in Malaysia. Such findings align with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) 8 and SDG 12, which directly and indirectly contribute to and emphasize the importance of decent work, economic growth, and responsible consumption and production.

Future research shall be focused on social media's influence on the selection of experiential tourism based on popularity and word of mouth. External factors such as peer pressure, social status, access to information and economic influences could be investigated to solidify the findings of this research which are solely on personal factors.

REFERENCES

- Bandura, A. (1986). Social foundations of thought and action: A social cognitive theory.
- Bandura, A. (1991). Social cognitive theory of moral thought and action. *Handbook of ethical behaviour and development*, p. 1, 45e103.
- Bilgihan, A., (2016). Gen Y customer loyalty in online shopping: an integrated model of trust, user experience and branding. *Computers in Human Behaviour*. 61, pp.103–113.
- Blank, C., Gatterer, K., Leichtfried, V., Pollhammer, D., Mair-Raggautz, M., Duschek, S., Humpeler, E. and Schobersberger, W., (2018). Short vacation improves stress-level and well-being in German-speaking middle-managers—A randomized controlled trial. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 15(1), p.130.
- Childers, T.L., Carr, C.L., Peck, J., Carson, S., (2002). Hedonic and utilitarian motivations for online retail shopping behaviour. *Journal of Retailing*. 77 (4), 511–535.
- Cooper, C. L., & Lu, L., (2016). Presenteeism as a global phenomenon: Unraveling the psychosocial mechanisms from the perspective of social cognitive theory. *Cross Cultural & Strategic Management*, 23(2), 216-231.
- Department of Statistics Malaysia (2019). Household Income and Basic Amenities Report, Department of Statistics, Malaysia, Retrieved from https://www.dosm.gov.my/v1/index.php?r=column/cthemByCat&cat=323&bul_id=c3JpRzRqeTNPamMxL1FpTkNBNUVBQT09&menu_id=amVoWU54UTl0a21NWmdhMjFMMWcyZz09, on July 11, 2022.
- Domestic Tourism Malaysia, (2021). <https://newss.statistics.gov.my/newss-portalx/ep/epProductCatalogForm.seam?cid=144665>, on July 11, 2022.
- Ipsos Malaysia (2021). Press Release: Pandemic's Impact on Malaysian Workforce. Retrieved from https://www.ipsos.com/sites/default/files/ct/news/documents/2021-01/ipsos_malaysia_press_release_-_pandemics_impact_on_malaysian_workforce_-_200121_final.pdf.
- Wagner, G., Schramm-Klein, H., Steinmann, S., (2016). E-Shopping acceptance: a qualitative and meta-analytic review. *Information & Management*. 52, 1, 44-60
- World Economic Forum (2021). 2020 was a record year for feeling stressed at work. Retrieved from <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/12/employees-stress-mental-health-workplace-environment/>, on July 11, 2022.